

Part of

Data management plan for "Development of Organic Chemosensors for Optical Detection of Biogenic Amines" project

Description

LCS FARP

Description

Optical detection of biogenic amines offers the potential for rapid, simple, and cost-effective determination, with potential applications ranging from food safety to medical diagnostics. This project aims to develop small molecule-based (quinone and/or indane derivatives) chemosensors and immobilized sensing materials for biogenic amine detection. Data generated by a variety of analytical techniques, including high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, and fluorescence (FL) spectroscopy, will be used to characterize the properties of sensors and sensing materials as well as their optical response towards biogenic amines.

Researchers

Nelli Batenko (0000-0002-2605-6980), Anastasija Gaile (0000-0001-7268-573X), svetlana zhzhkun (0000-0002-0568-1664)

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Research and development

Description

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data acquisition aims to characterize the optical properties of sensors (sensing materials) based on compounds with carbonyl functionalities. This includes detailed analysis of their spectral characteristics (e.g., absorption and emission), the investigation of their optical response upon interaction with biogenic amines.

The data will be acquired using the scientific equipment available at the Institute of Chemistry and Chemical Technology of the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Technology of RTU.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF

- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The obtained data will be valuable for researchers investigating organic chemosensors, structure-optical response relationships, and biogenic amine detection.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

CIF (Crystallographic Information Framework)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Data access will be restricted under an embargo for the duration of the project.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

RTU research data repository

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet browser

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-08

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2029-01-02

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

This work has been supported by grant No. RTU-ZG-2024/1-0028 under the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility funded project No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/003 "Implementation of consolidation and management changes at Riga Technical University, Liepaja University, Rezekne Academy of Technology, Latvian Maritime Academy and Liepaja Maritime College for the progress towards excellence in higher education, science, and innovation".

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Nelli Batenko (0000-0002-2605-6980)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Until the research data is published as open access, it will be password-protected and accessible solely to grant team members.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

